

FOAMED-METAL-REINFORCED COMPOSITES: TRIBOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF FOAMED COPPER FILLED WITH EPOXY-MATRIX POLYMER

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Abstract

In order to improve the thermal performance and wear resistance of polymers, foamed copper materials filled with a curable epoxy matrix have been developed for tribological studies. Graphite flakes were incorporated as friction additive in the epoxy matrix. The tribological properties of foamed-copper-reinforced composites were investigated using a UMT-2 friction and wear tester. An electric field was imposed between the specimen and the disk to monitor the formation of the transfer film by means of contact resistance. It was found that the foamed-copper-reinforced composites possess better wear resistance than homogeneous epoxy-matrix polymers, and the smaller the pore size of the foamed copper, the better the wear resistance. The friction coefficients increase for the locally direct contact between the copper and the steel disk. And the copper skeletons contribute to the timely transfer of friction heat and the load sharing. The temperature of the frictional area was measured using an infra-red thermal camera during the test. The foamed copper unit was modeled from the foaming mechanism of polyurethane, which served as a template. The temperature field of the sample and the effect of metallic skeletons on temperature were calculated by the finite element analysis (FEA). The actual temperature and the modeling analysis shows the foamed-copper-reinforced composites are effective in transmitting heat along the interconnected metallic skeletons, and therefore possess better thermal conductivity and wear resistance.

1 Introduction

In the field of tribology, polytetrafluoroethylene, polyoxymethylene, polyamide, epoxy resin (EP), and other polymer materials with different tribological characteristics are widely used as solid

lubricating materials [1-5]. However, since such materials have low thermal conductivity, their strength and wear resistance at high temperatures are limited. The friction heat at the interface tends not to dissipate and with rising temperatures caused by heat buildup, material properties weaken dramatically and may lead to failure [6, 7]. Because of these problems, researchers often dope polymer matrices with metal powder to improve the thermal conductivity of the polymer [8]. Generally speaking, a 3D continuous metallic skeletal structure is expected to help friction heat dissipate more quickly than discrete metal-particle-reinforced composites. Such continuous skeletons could play a double role in improving the polymer strength as well as enhancing heat dissipation.

An open-cell foamed metal has a porous structure with an interconnected 3D metallic network and possesses many special properties, such as low density, specific mechanical performance, high specific surface area, and high conductivity [9]. They have been used for structured templates and supports [10, 11], electrodes [12], heat radiators [13, 14], muffling devices [15], and so on. Although similar porous structures have been introduced for use in tribological materials [16-18], the tribology literature on foamed-metal-reinforced composites is scarce, probably because the preparation process is still in an early stage. Continuing from our previous experiments [19], here we describe foamed copper with an epoxy matrix polymer. The friction coefficients and wear rates of composites, as well as the temperature field of the sample in the friction process were investigated to better understand the influence of metallic skeletons on composite wear performance.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials preparation

Three kinds of foamed copper (pore density: 10, 20, 40 pores per inch (PPI), porosity: 96%, 93%, 89%) were fabricated by electroless copper plating on polyurethane (PU) foam, followed by electro-deposition and removal of non-conductive 3D substrates by burning (Fig. 1). The foamed copper samples had open-celled structures composed of dodecahedron-like cells with pentagonal or hexagonal faces, and the metallic skeletons were hollow. The samples were cut into suitable sizes by an ultra-thin diamond blade.

The matrix material was made from a commercial EP (E51, epoxy equivalent: 185-200 g/eq) cured by a polyamine hardener (618). Graphite flakes with an average particle size of 7 μm (Shanghai Colloid-Chemical Plant) were selected as the traditional filler. Dibutyl phthalate was used as toughener for epoxy resin, and a silane coupling agent was used for the modification of graphite.

The graphite flakes after being modified were kept in an oven at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h before the mixing process. EP components were also preheated to 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in order to decrease their viscosity for a thorough wetting of the filler material. After combining the filler with the resin, the mixture was mechanically dispersed under vacuum in order to distribute filler particles uniformly and remove trapped air, which could affect composite compactness significantly. The hardener was then added to the suspension, followed by stirring for about 3 min. Finally, the mixture was poured over the foamed copper in a silicone rubber mold and curing was allowed to proceed (Fig. 2a). To inhibit the precipitation of low-molecular-weight hydrocarbons during curing, the specimen was placed in an atmosphere furnace with nitrogen pressure 0.1 MPa and 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 h. The morphology of the foamed-copper-reinforced composite was shown in Fig. 2b, and the insets through the resulting composite material showed that the foamed copper was effectively encapsulated by the EP-matrix polymer. EP-matrix polymers containing the same fillers in the same amounts but without foamed copper were also made for comparison purposes. All test specimens were machined from the cured composite blocks.

Graphite was incorporated into the composites at 15 wt% which is in accordance with previous studies [20]. Table 1 summarizes all compositions and nomenclature for composites tested in this study. As an example of the naming system applied, a composite consisting of 34 wt% foamed copper (20 PPI), 15 wt% graphite, and epoxy (Balancing the

remaining content together with toughener and coupling agent) would be given the name EP-Gr-F20.

2.2. Friction and wear testing

Wear tests were conducted using a UMT-2 friction and wear tester (CETR, USA) (Fig. 3a). The composite specimen pin was rotated on a carburizing steel alloy disk in a pin-on-disk configuration, and the trajectory radius in the friction process was 25 mm. The sliding speed was always 0.26 m/s. The initial surface roughness of the disk $R_a=0.2 \mu\text{m}$. All tests were conducted for 2 h under dry conditions at room temperature. An electric field was imposed between the specimen and the disk to monitor the tribo-chemical reaction by means of contact resistance (Fig. 3b). The frictional coefficient was recorded and calculated using the ratio between the tangential force and the normal load, and its value was determined by averaging over an entire test. The mass loss of the composite specimen was measured after the wear test in order to calculate the specific wear rate using the following equation:

$$\dot{W}_s = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho F_N L} \quad (1)$$

In the equation, Δm is the specimen's mass loss, ρ is the density of the specimen, F_N is the normal load applied to the specimen during sliding, and L is the total sliding distance. Three repeated trials were conducted for each specimen, and the mean and standard deviation of frictional coefficients and wear rates were calculated by the three repeated trials.

The worn surfaces of composite specimens were observed using a digital microscope (VHX-600E, Keyence, Japan). The temperature of the frictional area was measured on the sample using an infra-red thermal camera (Fluke Ti25, Fluke, USA) at regular intervals during the test. The highest temperature reading of the frictional area on the infra-red photograph was used. The infra-red camera works by measuring heat emitted from surfaces and it was calibrated by photographing objects of a known temperature. Temperature readings were accurate within $< 0.1 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Room temperature was nearly constant during the experiments.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Friction and wear behavior

Fig. 4 shows the friction coefficients and wear rates of foamed-copper-reinforced composites and the homogeneous specimens at a velocity of 0.26 m/s and a pressure of 0.5 MPa. Fig. 4a shows that the

foamed-copper-reinforced composites possess higher friction coefficients than the homogeneous EP-matrix polymers. The increase in friction coefficient is caused by some direct contact between the copper skeletons and the steel disc at the frictional interface. The smaller the aperture of the foamed copper is, the larger the copper area present at this interface. Thus, the specimen EP-Gr-F40 shows the highest friction coefficient. The wear rates decrease as foamed copper is introduced to the composites (Fig. 4b). The foamed copper, with its natural porosity serving as the 3D skeletal support, restrains the plastic flow of the epoxy matrix and can serve as a lubricant reservoir for the contact surface.

Fig. 5a shows the friction coefficients and wear rates of EP-Gr-F40 and EP-Gr as a function of pressure at 0.26 m/s. The friction coefficients of EP-Gr-F40 decrease with increasing pressure, but are still higher overall when compared to the homogeneous EP-matrix polymer EP-Gr. The wear rates of foamed-copper-reinforced composite increase with increasing load, but are still at lower levels compared to the homogeneous polymer shown in Fig. 4b. Beneficial wear rates come from the favorable load-sharing and heat-dissipating qualities of the copper skeletons embedded in the EP-matrix polymer.

Fig. 6 shows typical variations in friction coefficients of the composite specimens and the homogeneous EP-matrix polymer specimens with sliding time. Fluctuations in friction coefficients for the foamed-copper-reinforced composites are similar to homologous polymer EP-Gr, and both are smoother than that of pure EP. The addition of graphite can effectively stabilize friction coefficients of the EP-matrix polymer.

The circuit between the foamed-copper-reinforced composite and steel disk was shown to be intact by monitoring of the DC contact resistance using a circuit tester shown in Fig. 3b. The reasons were that there were some direct contacts between the copper skeletons and the steel disk during the sliding process on one hand, and on the other hand, some copper scraps were likely to succumb to the shear stress and then quickly and ceaselessly intervene into the frictional interface forming the transfer layer. In other words, the skeletons of foamed copper impeded the formation of an integral transfer film. This may also explain why the foamed copper led to an increase in the friction coefficient. Although it had a negative impact on the solid-lubricating process in most cases, it would still be beneficial to reduce the contact resistance and avoid

impeding electrical contact under some current-carrying conditions.

3.2 Wear mechanism analysis

Fig. 7 shows the micrographs of worn surfaces of foamed-copper-reinforced composites and a homogeneous EP-matrix polymer at 0.26 m/s and 0.5 MPa. Fig. 7a, b, and c show that the worn surfaces of foamed-copper-reinforced composites contained prominent veins of malleable copper. The smaller the aperture of the foamed copper was, the more copper appeared at the interface.

Compared with the homogeneous specimen EP-Gr (Fig. 7d), some slight marks of hard particle erosion and plastic furrow deformation can be seen on the resinous part of the worn surface of EP-Gr-F40 (Fig. 7e). Plastic flow of EP-matrix polymer can also be seen along the sliding direction of the contacting surface, which was originated and extended by friction heat, pressure, and shear force.

Some fragmentary lubricants attach to and/or penetrate the surfaces and cavities of the visible copper skeletons (Fig. 7f). These cavities belonging to the hollow skeletons serve to collect and store lubricant on friction surfaces. As a result of the some direct contact between the copper and the steel disk, proved by contact resistance measurements, the copper skeletons at the frictional interface shared the load directly, which in turn improved wear resistance.

Based on the friction performance and high thermal and electrical conductivities of foamed-copper-reinforced composites, potential applications include brake assemblies and electric brushes.

3.3. Friction model and thermal effect analysis

In order to better understand the influence of metallic skeletons on the wear performance of the composite, the temperature fields of the composites were simulated by the finite element analysis (FEA).

According to the morphology and the forming mechanism of foamed copper, we established a sphere-centered tetrakaidecahedron structure starting from the precursor PU foam to model the cell of foamed copper. This tetrakaidecahedron has eight regular hexagons and six squares, which represent the frothing process of PU (Fig. 8a). An air bubble is generated from the melting PU matrix, which grows up gradually and reaches a balanced status, e.g., attains the minimum

possible surface energy [21]. From here, it forms a sphere-centered approximate tetrakaidecahedron structure after being solidified. Modeling parameters based on this frothing process contain two basic variables: the side length of the tetrakaidecahedron (m) and the radius of the sphere-shaped air bubble (r). Starting from the integrity of frothing (the air bubble intersects with every surface of the tetrakaidecahedron, but maintains the integrity of every surface), the relationship between m and r is as follows:

$$\sqrt{2} < \frac{r}{m} < \frac{3}{2} \quad (2)$$

Through measurement, the side length of the tetrakaidecahedron was $m = 0.15$ mm (40 PPI). Matching between unit bodies forms a topological structure of foamed metal. From the matching process we can conclude that the surface area of the foamed unit body is the area of intersection between the air bubble and the tetrakaidecahedron, i.e., the internal surface of the foam unit in Fig. 8a.

The area ratio of copper at the friction interface φ can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\varphi = \frac{S_{Cu}}{S_{Int}} \quad (3)$$

where S_{Cu} is surface area of copper at the friction interface and S_{Int} is the area of the friction interface.

Here, we choose two kinds of typical contact models, model I and II (Fig. 8b). The area ratios can be calculated as follows

$$\varphi_1 = 2\pi + 1 - \pi \left(\frac{r}{m} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}\pi}{3} + 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{3}\pi}{9} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{m} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

Substitute formula (2) into (4) and (5), we can obtain the area ratio of copper at the friction interface:

$$21.5\% < \varphi_1 < 100\%; 9.3\% < \varphi_2 < 39.6\% \quad (6)$$

It can be seen that the area ratio of copper at the friction interface is a dynamically changing parameter. Models I and II are only

two kinds of typical contact models. Combined with micrographs of the worn surfaces, we can infer that the distribution of copper at the interface is random and asymmetric, and that the greater the pore density, the easier it is to predict the distribution of copper.

The temperature distribution of EP-Gr and EP-Gr-F40 as selected specimens in the friction process based on both the infrared thermography and FEA is shown in Fig. 9. The variations of the maximum temperature with testing time at 0.5 MPa, 0.26 m/s are shown in Fig. 9a. The maximum temperatures here were recorded by the infrared thermography at intervals of 10 minutes, which serve as the temperatures of friction interfaces. It shows the temperature heads towards stability, and a balance between heat generation and dissipation can be achieved in the friction process. At the early stage, the heat-source effect of the copper skeletons was dominant; then, with the form of transfer layer, the heat dissipation emerged as the heat source effect became weakened. That's also the reason that the specimen EP-Gr-F40 has a lower friction temperature than the homologous polymer EP-Gr. The temperature fields for EP-Gr and EP-Gr-F40 at the 30-minute mark are taken as representative (Fig. 9b and c). It can be seen that the radial temperature grade of foamed-copper-reinforced composite is smaller owing to the copper skeletons with bigger heat transfer rate. These infrared images display directly that the foamed copper is helpful to transfer of friction heat timely.

Fig. 9d shows the FEA of temperature of foamed-copper-reinforced composite based on model I. The result of steady-state temperature of the specimen cell is consistent with the experimental result basically. This simulated image reflects the influence of the metallic skeletons on the temperature gradient of specimen cell, especially of epoxy matrix (Fig. 9e and f). The friction heat is conducted through the 3D supporting skeletons effectively, regardless of the heat source effect of the metallic skeletons on the friction surface. The interconnected 3D metallic skeletons of foamed copper can restrain plastic deformation and operate to pack and fix the tribological fillers,

and help composites have good thermal and electrical conductivities. Friction heat and/or electric current can be conducted along the 3D skeletal support effectively.

4 Conclusions

Foamed-copper-reinforced composites were fabricated effectively by filling with the liquid epoxy matrix containing graphite. The curing process was assisted by positive pressure in order to inhibit the precipitation of low-molecular-weight hydrocarbons, thus to improve the compactness of the composite.

The friction coefficients increase as foamed copper was introduced into the composites for some direct contact between the copper and the steel disk during the sliding process, which was supported by the DC contact resistance. The decrease in wear rate was a benefit of the timely transfer of friction heat as well as the load-sharing of metallic skeletons of foamed copper. The smaller the foamed copper aperture was, the better the wear resistance of the composite. Hard particle erosion and plastic furrow deformation were the main wear mechanisms on the worn surfaces of the foamed-copper-reinforced composites.

The cell of foamed copper was modeled from the precursor PU foam. The area ratio of copper at the friction interface was quantified based on two kinds of typical contact models. The result of FEA of foamed-copper-reinforced composite based on model I was consistent basically with the experimental result from infrared thermography. The influence of the metallic skeletons on the temperature gradient of specimen was displayed visually.

The interconnected 3D metallic skeletons of foamed copper can inhibit plastic deformation and play the role of packing and fixing the EP-matrix polymer. More importantly, the foamed copper enhances the thermal conductivity of composites effectively, and provides a new idea for design of wear-resistant materials.

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Table

Table 1. Composition and nomenclature for tested composites.

Nomenclature	Foamed copper (wt%)	Graphite (wt%)	Density (g/cm ³)
EP-Gr	—	15	1.03
EP-Gr-F10	22 (10 PPI)	15	1.13
EP-Gr-F20	34 (20 PPI)	15	1.18
EP-Gr-F40	41 (40 PPI)	15	1.27

Figures:

Fig. 1. Preparation processes and subsequent morphology of foamed copper.

Fig. 2. The epoxy matrix filling method in the preparation of composites (a), and the morphology of the foamed-copper-reinforced composites, with the insets showing typical copper skeleton distributed in the surface (b).

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the UMT-2 friction and wear tester (a) and the set-up for the calculation of contact resistance (b).

Fig. 4. The values of friction coefficients (a) and wear rates (b) of selected specimens at a velocity of 0.26 m/s and a pressure of 0.5 MPa.

Fig. 5. The friction coefficients (a) and wear rates (b) of EP-Gr-F40 and EP-Gr as a function of pressure at 0.26 m/s.

Fig. 6. The variations in friction coefficients of specimens with sliding duration at 0.26 m/s and 0.5 MPa.

Fig. 7. Optical micrographs of the worn surfaces of composites EP-Gr-F10 (a), EP-Gr-F20 (b), EP-Gr-F40 (c, e, and f), and EP-Gr (d) at 0.26 m/s and 0.5 MPa.

Fig. 8. Modeling of the foamed-copper cell from the precursor PU foam (a), and two kinds of typical contact models based on the area ratio of copper at the friction interface (b).

Fig. 9. The temperature distribution of selected specimens in the friction process based on both the infrared thermography and FEA (a: variations of the measuring maximum temperature with testing time at 0.5 MPa, 0.26 m/s; b and c: the direct measurements of temperature fields for EP-Gr and EP-Gr-F40 at the 30-minute mark; d: the steady-state thermal analysis of the friction system of foamed-copper-reinforced composite based on model I; e and f: the impact of foamed copper on temperature fields of epoxy matrix).